

IMPACT OF DIRECT COMMUNICATION RADIO BROADCASTS ON LISTENING CULTURE

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Аннотация.

Мақолада бевосита мулоқотли радиоэшиттиришларнинг тингловчиларга таъсири, унинг ўзига хос томонлари, ижобий, салбий жиҳатлари, тарбиявий аҳамиятлари ҳақида сўз юритилган.

Таянч сўзлар.

радиоаудитория, радиоканал, бевосита эшиттиришлар, мулоқот, маданият, тарбия, одоб.

Аннотация.

В статье рассказывается о влиянии радиопередачи прямого общения на слушателей, ее специфических аспектах, положительных, отрицательных сторонах, воспитательном значении.

Базовые слова.

радиожурналистика, радиоканал, прямые трансляции, коммуникация, культура, воспитание, этикет.

Abstract.

The article describes the influence of the radio broadcast of direct communication on listeners, its specific aspects, positive, negative sides, educational significance.

Basic words.

It is no secret that there is an increase in the number of live radio broadcasts these days. Listeners regularly listen to many state and non-state radio channels. Each of them has its own uniqueness. Of course, there are advantages and disadvantages. Each radio channel broadcasts its broadcasts based on its target audience. With the variety of radio broadcasts and the large number of listeners, state and non-state radio channels gain great importance. In general, when choosing a topic, a journalist should choose a topic that is both propaganda and campaigning, and, moreover, the most important thing is to motivate young people and get enthusiasm from their practical work. This is the basic condition of the skill.

a number of unique aspects of communicating with listeners through the

medium of radio . Such communication is carried out without meaningful situations (mimicry, gesture, pantomime) that convey great spirituality or emotionality to the audience. It does not have a direct opposite connection to correct the words that have been mistakenly omitted. There is no direct dialogue with the audience that includes comments and objections. For a radio journalist, there is no specific audience or setting that receives his broadcast. All this makes the process of radio communication somewhat difficult. Not knowing the specifics of radio means not being able to take advantage of the potential of this powerful media. Two simultaneous messages on a given topic may make a deep impression, while the other may leave no impression at all. In order to prevent this from happening, the material allocated for the radio, its volume, the amount of information included, the style of expression, speech pronunciation, language should be adapted to the specific characteristics and qualities of the listeners.

Of course, when a radio journalist prepares a broadcast, he does not directly know his listeners, his composition, their thoughts and concerns at that moment, what he is doing at the same time, etc. But he should know the general laws of listeners' mind, what psychological mechanisms work in receiving oral radio messages.

The concept that experts hold that communication plays an important role in the reception of a radio message. Communication means that there is a connection between the journalist and the audience . It can be said that an informal "symbolic" dialogue begins between the journalist and the audience. On-air communication and on-air communication are similar concepts. But at the same time, these are separate, dissimilar concepts. Communication only **establishes interaction, initiates cooperation. In this process, the listener becomes immersed in the content of the radio message.** Being in a relationship has a stronger and deeper character , and in this process the psyche of the listener falls into the psyche of a journalist. During the narration of the events, he is sometimes sad, sometimes happy, sometimes angry. Attitude is a key factor in achieving the intended purpose of radio broadcasting .

of radio with the audience starts from the first moments of broadcasting . The beginning of communication can be defined as the moment when the listener gets hold of the radio broadcast program and begins to familiarize himself with its content . In this, of course, the term "communication" is used in many senses . Another common form of communication is direct invitations to the audience to engage in various forms of informal engagement. In our opinion , the journalist has a close cooperation with the audience through in relation to

be good effect goes _ Because in this , the journalist is the listener didn't notice without it n ing and _ _ knowledge level increase regarding seriously _ _ _ I 'm going .

The method of invitation to cooperation helps both journalists and listeners to unite into one general audience. This has important psychological significance for listeners. Often, journalists start a conversation with abstract comments that do not have a direct connection to the subject of the conversation and the object of information. This distracts the audience, the listeners cannot understand what the speech is about. Piro v behind news t to the consciousness of hearing reached doesn't go This and journalistic work zoe he said he left is a word . After announcing the name and purpose of the broadcast, without giving any lyrics to the broadcast, it will not be successful to start like a song.

V. D. Pelt, professor of Moscow State University, wrote: "Experienced publicists, local reporters, editors also take into account the psychological capabilities of readers and listeners. It has been scientifically proven that a person can read, hear and accept only a small amount of information. This especially radio message oral ra v at work going one in the circumstances very important _

How is the media audience changing in today's news society? It can be said with confidence that the audience is becoming active as a result of the given opportunities and is trying to fully demonstrate its individual characteristics. The audience has become the main factor determining the level of information provided. Media that do not know their fans well and do not take into account their demands cannot withstand the competition in the information market. At the same time, there is an increase in the number of types of specialized mass media that do not adapt to the audience, but try to increase its level. In general, the audience has a choice as a consumer of information, accepting the news material they like and not paying attention to what they don't like. Today's specialists face the task of protecting the audience from various information attacks and false information. Each audience member must be extremely vigilant about information security issues. If a small amount of information creates an information deficit, the flow of information can harm the psyche of the audience, in any case depends on the information consumer's understanding of what he wants. In this case, the general level, outlook, and will of the audience are extremely important.

It is very convenient for the audience to express their opinion in a playful way, sitting at home or without being interrupted from the work they are doing. Voluntary feedback on quizzes or interesting interactive programs does not carry the same responsibility as filling out questionnaires or participating in sociological

research. In this, the fan does not feel too serious. The most important thing is that Shinavanda will connect to the air whenever he wants. Hence, his thoughts will be sincere and free of obligation and artificiality. A fan expressing an opinion on a topic wants to see a sincere reaction from the presenter. Commenting becomes as natural to the audience representative as a conversation or meeting in everyday life. The factors listed above determine how well interactive programs can engage an audience.

Journalists are making a worthy contribution to the updates and achievements in the country with their talent, sharp pen, and selfless work. In this regard, various contests, creative contests, grant projects, and social programs that serve the development of our journalism are gaining importance. The scale of radio broadcasts, their artistic level, and their role in social life began to gain distinction. Including, since the establishment of the radio channels of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, they have been enriched with spiritual-educational, social-political and, at the same time, entertainment broadcasts. It is known that according to experts, "the nature of radio requires oral speech." Therefore, every journalist who communicates should choose words that can find a way to the listener's heart, understandable and close to his heart. Since ancient times, people believed in the divine power of the word and its miraculous effect. A good wish, a happy tone lifts the mood of the listener, while a depressing voice has a negative effect. Every listener, regardless of age, nationality, or education, who turns to the radio remains an ordinary listener. The mood of the listener is influenced by tone, intonation, noise and music. Every radio journalist who comes to the microphone must feel the responsibility and accountability to thousands of listeners, their mood and spirit .

The responsibility of the journalist who conducts direct communication increases in front of the broadcast. Because every mistake he makes reaches the ears of thousands of listeners without change. The author has no control over the word that goes on the airwaves. In the experience of the journalists of the radio channel of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, it can be said that such cases hardly ever occur. The knowledge and skill of a radio journalist, radio presenter is one of the main signs of his creative identity. Practical knowledge is closely related to the general social orientation of a person. Thinking skills such as analysis, synthesis, and generalization play an important role in the formation of a radio journalist. Sometimes a radio journalist who prepares material on a topic he does not know well will drastically lower the level of broadcasting. Such cases may

be due to the inexperience of the journalist who invited a guest to a talk show and was not prepared for the topic.

The ideological and educational value of live broadcasts is also the formation of public opinion and the promotion of the right opinion. However, it is necessary to achieve such a result that the listeners themselves draw the true conclusion. In this matter, it is advisable for a radio journalist to be only intelligent, not to express his opinion when asking questions (as an exception, an example can be given), and also not to make "wisdom" by saying smart things. Direct communication broadcasts of the radio channels of the National Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan quickly became popular because they were free from the mentioned defects. Today's Talk managed to attract listeners with its unfinished, inconclusive ending. Because of this, live broadcasts have become the most popular broadcasts. Be it intellectual, social, or domestic, his broadcasts, which reached the diversity of topics and ideas, became the glory of the radio.

Determining the priorities of the TV and radio channels and regional divisions of the MTRK of Uzbekistan, ensuring their economic independence and competitiveness in the market of information services, implementing the market mechanism in the process of organizing television and radio broadcasts and broadcasting, attracting investments from our country and foreign enterprises, organizations and financial institutions in this field.

Further development of the technology market in accordance with modern requirements and standards, development and implementation of measures for the introduction of information, computer and media technologies to the preparation of television and radio programs. Broadcasters, like other mass media, must constantly update their programs. News, new broadcasts are always in the attention of listeners. In accordance with these, employees of radio editorial offices regularly work on new projects.

When a journalist prepares a broadcast, he does it step by step. First of all, he should find evidence and literature on the topic to be discussed and study it carefully. Although the preparation of one radio broadcast is carried out by several technical and creative staff, the biggest burden falls on the radio journalist. Preparing a broadcasting project, gathering experts in the field of the emerging topic, calculating their time, and most importantly asking relevant questions about the topic require strong skills from every journalist. Only the possessor of strong skills can create a project of direct interactive broadcasts at the level of today's demand.

it is very important for every radio journalist to gather knowledge and skills, to creatively and critically accept the acquired practice, to be able to direct his activity correctly from the socio-political point of view of the time. The skill of a radio journalist can be determined only when the worldview is at a high level, and the skills are tested in practice for a long time and continuously. In particular, every radio journalist who communicates directly should work tirelessly before the broadcast, work on his words, emotions, dialect, and self-control in front of the microphone. Thirst for information, curiosity is one of the main characteristics of a radio journalist.

Observability of a journalist is necessary for the correct analysis of events in social life. When choosing a topic for broadcasting, a radio journalist who takes into account what interests the listener, what unsolved problem forces him to call, can choose a topic that is relevant today. Of course, the listener should know the level of his audience.

In conclusion, it is difficult to make a one-sided analysis of the skills of a radio journalist in the preparation of broadcasts with direct communication. However, these facts, the materials collected by a radio journalist for broadcasting, the people involved in the broadcasting and the arguments they bring serve to determine its potential.

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